

Quick report

Reactions to an anti Sars-CoV-2 mRNA Booster (3rd shot)

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Contrary to occasional fears, boosting the Corona vaccine with a 3rd dose is not associated with poorer tolerability. This is shown by feedback the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has received so far from users of the "v-safe" app, which the agency developed specifically as a vigilance system for SARS-CoV-2.

The results were published in Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report (2021; DOI: 10.15585/mmwr.mm7039e4).

As of September 19, 2021 2.2 million people in the United States have already received their 3rd dose of COVID-19 vaccine. The FDA had approved a booster with the Moderna and Biontech/Pfizer vaccines on Aug. 12 for patients with moderate or severe immune deficiency (approval of the Biontech/Pfizer vaccine has since been extended to all seniors as well as younger people at increased risk of infection).

Tolerability data were limited to relatively few individuals in the pivotal studies. Biontech/Pfizer's Phase 3 trial of BNT162b2 enrolled just 306 people. Feedback from users of the "v-safe" app was therefore eagerly awaited. It had been feared that the boost, which leads to a significant increase in antibody titers, would also be associated with increased side effects. There has been little sign of that, according to the report by CDC's Anne Hause, Atlanta, and collaborators. So far, 22,191 "v-safe" users have submitted their experiences. The 3rd dose had occurred a median of 182 days (interquartile range 160 to 202 days) after the 2nd dose.

Local adverse events at the injection site were reported by 16,615 subjects (74.9%). These included pain at the injection site in 15,761 vaccinees (71.0%). Systemic reactions occurred in 15,503 subjects (69.9%). The most common were fatigue (12,429 subjects; 56.0%) and headache (9,636 subjects; 43.4%).

For BNT162b2 from Biontech/Pfizer, the rate of local side effects increased from 71.7% after the 2nd dose to 74.1% after the 3rd dose. For systemic side effects, there was a decrease from 71.7% to 69.2%. For Moderna's mRNA-1273, the proportion with local side effects increased from 83.5% to 84.7%. There was a decrease in systemic adverse events from 81.3% to 79.0%.

Reporting of serious complications such as anaphylaxis, myocarditis/epicarditis, or Guillain-Barré syndrome cannot be expected from users of the app. Here, CDC relies on reports from physicians or other providers in the Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System (VAERS). No experience has yet been published on this.

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Conflicts of interest

None.

References

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